

USSR music samizdat collections and Latvian items in them

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2020.08.20.

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.3992721

Over the past twelve years, we have seen an increase in the number of samizdat collections globally. In addition, these collections have been ever more systematically mapped, audited, organized, and digitized. The largest public collection of music-oriented samizdat of the USSR era is believed to be in the US: the **‘Russian rock/Youth Counterculture “zine” Collection’** is held at the Global Resources Center at the George Washington University Library.¹ It covers the period from 1977 to 1998 and contains about 200 items.²

The second largest collection can be found in Moscow, **‘Kollekcija netradicionnoj pečati’** (*Коллекция нетрадиционной печати*)³, *Gosudarstvennaya Publichnaya Istoricheskaya Biblioteka Rossii* (GPIB). Of the 7,000 titles of the periodicals (about 80,000 editions), approximately 30 could be attributed to the genre of music-oriented samizdat.⁴

Other well-known samizdat archives and library collections, such as ‘Samizdat and other periodicals - The former USSR’ at the Forschungsstelle Osteuropa in Bremen⁵; Budapest “Samizdat and Emigré Publications” at Blinken OSA⁶; *The Memorial Research Center’s catalog of samizdat*⁷ are believed to have a much smaller number of music-oriented editions. The samizdat content of these and other repositories is not properly cataloged, nor is its content publicly available in its entirety; therefore, their collections cannot be judged remotely.

¹ See recollection of how it was made: Mark Yoffe, ‘Soviet Rock Collection and International Counterculture Archive at the Global Resources Center of the George Washington University Libraries’, *Slavic & East European Information Resources*, 2020, 1–21.

² ‘Selected Specialized Collections in the GRC. Russia/Soviet Union & Eastern and Central European Collections’, The George Washington University Libraries and Academic Innovation, 2020, <http://library.gwu.edu>.

³ “Коллекция нетрадиционной печати”, Центр социально-политической истории, Государственная публичная историческая библиотека России (ГПИБ) [The State public historical library of the RSFSR] (http://www.shpl.ru/readers/centr_sotcialino_politicheskoy_istorii/funds3/kollekzya_netraditzionnoi_pechati)

⁴ Elena Strukova to Jānis Daugavietis, ‘Sovetskij Muzikalnij Samizdat’, 12 March 2020.

⁵ Samizdat and other Periodicals, The Research Centre for East European Studies (Forschungsstelle Osteuropa – FSO), https://www.forschungsstelle.uni-bremen.de/en/9/20111208113007/Samizdat_Periodicals.html

⁶ the Vera and Donald Blinken Open Society Archives, Central European University (Közép-európai Egyetem), <http://catalog.osaarchivum.org>

⁷ Memorial online database “Samizdat Catalogue” - <http://samizdat.memo.ru>

The same is true of private collections, such as probably the largest: the **‘Archives of Aleksandr Kushnir’** (Kushnir Production / PR-agency), formerly known as the *Archives of Rock Samizdat of the Journal Kontr Kul't Ur'a* (*Архив рок самиздата журнала Контр Культ Ур'а*).

Also worth mentioning is the **‘Soviet Samizdat Periodicals’**⁸, an electronic catalog of the University of Toronto Libraries, published in 2015, which collects metadata from several publications and archives on USSR samizdat until 1986.⁹ It includes 45 music-oriented editions.

None of these archives or libraries offer full-text editions, although this is increasingly accepted practice in public libraries, not only in the EU but also elsewhere. The main concern is the unclear copyright issues.¹⁰

These copyright issues have not disrupted the work of citizen scientists/activists in the Russian blogosphere, which has allowed fans and collectors of USSR and post-Soviet music editions to create the largest collection of digital music samizdat. In recent years, this work has been concentrated in *Vkontakte*, the most popular social network in Russia, in the group **‘Vystavka - Muzej’ Russkoe Podpol'e. Oskolki’** (*Выставка - Музей’ Русское Подполье. Осколки*)¹¹. The group regularly publishes scanned editions in *.pdf and other formats, which are available as full texts and for free to members of the group. The collection of this group is not limited to the music-oriented samizdat of Soviet times, i.e. magazines and newspapers. It also includes periodicals that were produced following the collapse of the USSR, including books dedicated to Soviet/Russian rock music. Although the number of Soviet music-oriented samizdat in this collection is unknown, it is constantly increasing and can be assumed to come to at least a few hundred titles and thousands of editions.¹²

The degree to which Latvian music-oriented samizdat is represented in public libraries and archives of Latvia and the wider world is practically unresearched. Judging by the publicly available electronic catalogs, the collections of the Russian and US institutions contain far more editions than the Latvian ones. Some editions may be in the collection but not properly registered and processed. It can be assumed that a large part of the music-oriented samizdat is in private collections, most often un-systematised: ‘somewhere in the basement’, ‘attic’, ‘top-shelf’ or ‘under the bed’.

⁸ ‘Soviet Samizdat Periodicals’, University of Toronto Libraries - <https://samizdat.library.utoronto.ca>

⁹ Ann Komaromi, ‘Soviet Samizdat Periodicals’, University of Toronto Libraries, 2015, <https://samizdat.library.utoronto.ca/>; Allan Reid, ‘The Project for the Study of Dissidence and Samizdat: An Interview with Ann Komaromi’, *Canadian Slavonic Papers* 58, no. 4 (21 October 2016): 398–403, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00085006.2016.1239859>.

¹⁰ Veronika Trotter, ‘A Digital Voice for Russian Rock: Perspectives on Digitization of Russian Rock Zines’, *Slavic & East European Information Resources* 20, no. 1–2 (3 April 2019): 31–38, <https://doi.org/10.1080/15228886.2019.1628499>.

¹¹ https://vk.com/club71455498?w=wall-71455498_3694

¹² Archive storage - https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1xStfirt-tBciHRPO0V3sCRNsr_DcNXoNA

If we are to specifically assess the availability of *Ot Vinta* (От Винта)¹³ in public institutions, the preliminary study shows that not one of its eight issues is in Latvian libraries. There is, however, one issue in the GPIB¹⁴ and one in the George Washington University Library collections.¹⁵ In addition to this, three are roaming the Russian blogosphere in digital form. All the issues, including the originals, i.e. printed copies of the typewriter with the pasted original photographs, are located in the private collection of the magazine editor, Sergey Volchenko (Сергей Волченко), in Riga.¹⁶

Bibliography

- Komaromi, Ann. 'Soviet Samizdat Periodicals'. University of Toronto Libraries, 2015.
<https://samizdat.library.utoronto.ca/>.
- Reid, Allan. 'The Project for the Study of Dissidence and Samizdat: An Interview with Ann Komaromi'. *Canadian Slavonic Papers* 58, no. 4 (21 October 2016): 398–403.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00085006.2016.1239859>.
- The George Washington University Libraries and Academic Innovation. 'Selected Specialized Collections in the GRC. Russia/Soviet Union & Eastern and Central European Collections', 2020.
<http://library.gwu.edu>.
- Strukova, Elena. Letter to Jānis Daugavietis. 'Sovetskij Muzikalnij Samizdat', 18 February 2019.
———. Letter to Jānis Daugavietis. 'Sovetskij Muzikalnij Samizdat', 12 March 2020.
- Trotter, Veronika. 'A Digital Voice for Russian Rock: Perspectives on Digitization of Russian Rock Zines'. *Slavic & East European Information Resources* 20, no. 1–2 (3 April 2019): 31–38.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/15228886.2019.1628499>.
- Volchenko, Sergei. Interview [in Russian] with Sergei Volchenko (Сергей Волченко), 2019.10.29.
Interview by Jānis Daugavietis, 29 October 2019. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3522363>.
- Yoffe, Mark. 'Soviet Rock Collection and International Counterculture Archive at the Global Resources Center of the George Washington University Libraries'. *Slavic & East European Information Resources*, 2020, 1–21.
- . Letter to Jānis Daugavietis. '«От Винта»', 14 November 2019.

¹³ Russian-language music samizdat 'magazine' from the Latvian SSR which was published in the late Soviet period. It came out in Riga between 1987 and 1991 and was closely connected to the local underground and semi-official rock scene.

¹⁴ Elena Strukova to Jānis Daugavietis, 'Sovetskij Muzikalnij Samizdat', 18 February 2019.

¹⁵ Mark Yoffe to Jānis Daugavietis, '«От Винта»', 14 November 2019.

¹⁶ Sergei Volchenko, Interview [in Russian] with Sergei Volchenko (Сергей Волченко), 2019.10.29., interview by Jānis Daugavietis, 29 October 2019, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3522363>.